

SZ-HB-I-01 Research the language requirements for an exchange semester (English)

Author	@Julia Lehmler ; @Ricarda Peil (original German version) @Jan Martin Kauter ; @Tara-Marie Endries ; @Emily Penk (English translation)
Doi	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14930909
ID	SZ-HB-I-01
Title	Research the language requirements for an exchange semester
Educational area	#higher-education #adult-education
Persona	P. Kaja - Student https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10091286
Short description	Kaja needs proof of her French language skills for a semester abroad in France and is looking for an online language test.
Result	Kaja uses BIRD to take a language proficiency test and receives a digital certificate.
Process	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Problem scenario• Activity scenario<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Process "Search for language proficiency test (french)
Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Kaja is registered at BIRD• Kaja is logged in to BIRD
Components	#learningpathfinder #profile #data-wallet #workspace
Services / tools	

Problem scenario

Introduction

Kaja Stantke is planning an Erasmus exchange semester in France to improve her French skills and broaden her horizons. Kaja already has basic language skills, but no official proof of them. Kaja needs to find out what level is required for the Erasmus program and whether proof of existing language skills is required.

Problem definition

The Erasmus scholarship is highly sought after, and Kaja is worried about whether her current French skills, which are sufficient for everyday conversation. Furthermore, her previous knowledge isn't verified by any official language test. This raises the question of what level is required for the semester abroad in France, and whether proof of this is

required. If so, Kaja needs to find a suitable language aptitude test, ideally one available online.

Background and context

Kaja is pursuing a career in international politics, possibly in the European Parliament in Strasbourg, and therefore needs a good command of French. The Erasmus program would be an excellent opportunity to improve her French skills during a semester abroad in France.

Impact of the problem (on the Persona)

Kaja is under a lot of pressure because French universities usually expect level B2, which Kaja may not achieve. Some universities may even accept a B1 level, depending on the program requirements. Frequently required certificates are DELF B2 or DALF C1. Some universities also accept online language tests such as the Test de Français International (TFI) or offer their own tests. However, the requirements are confusing and difficult to understand.

Pre BIRD attempts at a solution

Kaja has already tried to find information about the required language skills, certificates, and possible test dates using various search engines and found it stressful and confusing. Kaja would have to research every single university in France to check their language level requirements.

Activity scenario

Process "Search for language proficiency test (french)

Step 1: Kaja opens the LearningPathFinder and enters the term "French language aptitude test" in the search bar.

Step 2: The LearningPathFinder suggests several language aptitude test providers for Kaja:

- Checklists from external providers (University Language Learning Center, [Institut Français](#), [VHS](#), Goethe-Institut, etc.)
- Scholarships for language courses aboard ([PROMS-Program](#), [DAAD scholarships database](#))
- Offers for language certificates (e.g., language certificates for the University of Dresden: [All Courses | E-Languages \(uni-leipzig.de\)](#), language tests, including online language placement tests)

Step 3: Kaja compares details such as test duration, costs, certifications, and specific requirements of French universities and finds a suitable test ([TFI – Test de Français International](#)) that comprehensively evaluates language skills and is accepted by the desired university.

Step 4: Kaja clicks on the selected test, reads the detailed information, and discovers that the test is available online and can be taken at short notice.

Step 5: Kaja registers for the test by filling out a form and prepares to take it.

Step 6: Kaja completes the test according to the instructions and receives immediate feedback and a certificate confirming her language skills upon completion.

Step 7: Kaja sees from the certificate that her French skills correspond to level B1, which, according to the coordinator, is sufficient for applying for an Erasmus semester in France.

Step 8: Kaja saves the certificate in the Datawallet.